

“RBP-ReguNet”

Deliverable 5.2

Annual DC reports: local training for all DCs and Network-training activities

PROJECT INFORMATION

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CONTACT	info@rbp-regunet.eu

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AUTHORS	Alessandro Provenzani, Ashwin Woodhoo & Adrián Posado
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LIST OF BENEFICIARIES AND PARTNER ORGANIZATIONS

ORGANIZATION	COUNTRY	ROLE	NAME	ACADEMY	DC
USC	SPAIN	C	Prof. Ashwin Woodhoo	academy	1
USC	SPAIN	B	Dr. Marta Varela Rey	academy	2
IC	FRANCE	B	Prof. Stephan Vagner	academy	3
CRG	SPAIN	B	Prof. Fátima Gebauer	academy	4
CRG	SPAIN	B	Prof. Juan Valcárcel	academy	5
SANQ	NETHERLANDS	B	Prof. Monika Wolkers	academy	6
IMMAG	ITALY	B	Dr. Massimiliano Clamer	non-academy	8
UNITN	ITALY	B	Prof. Alessandro Provenzani	academy	9
UMIL	ITALY	B	Prof. Pierfausto Seneci	academy	10
EMBL	GERMANY	B	Prof. Mathias Hentze	academy	11
MRC-CVR	UK	AP	Prof. Alfredo Castello	academy	7
KAERTOR	SPAIN	AP	Prof. Mabel Loza	non-academy	
CNR	ITALY	AP	Dr. Daniela Arosio	academy	
UPSACLAY	FRANCE	AP-B		academy	
UPF	SPAIN	AP-B		academy	
UVA	NETHERLANDS	AP-B		academy	

GLOSSARY OF ACRONYMS

CTS	Courses on Transferable Skills
DC	Doctoral Candidate
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
MSCA	Marie Skłodowska Curie Actions
PCDP	Personal Career Development Plan
SB	Supervisory Board
TDC	Training/Doctoral Studies Committee

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

RBP-ReguNet project is designed to harness recent discoveries and develop state-of-the-art research work to identify druggable targets across a spectrum of untreated diseases, encompassing cancer, neurological disorders, liver diseases, and infectious diseases. Our main aspiration within RBP-ReguNet is to establish and merge with the research work an advanced training program rooted in basic research yet bearing a significant impact on clinical translation. This program is already delivering comprehensive multidisciplinary scientific training, spanning computational, structural, molecular, and cellular biology to medicinal chemistry and pharmacological screening, fostering the next generation of European researchers in an intersectoral setting. This environment aims to propel ambitious and high-impact research focused on developing new therapies based on RBP biology.

RBP-ReguNet is mentoring 11 young scientists through their individual research projects aiming to translate fundamental discoveries into actionable druggable targets, by employing a multidisciplinary and intersectoral strategy that exposes the researchers to diverse methodologies, disciplines, and knowledge.

The specific training in the main laboratories, combined with secondments in complementary disciplines at host laboratories as well as a set of research and inter-sectoral network training will provide the doctoral candidates (DCs) with a deep understanding of their field of research, while at the same time attaining a broad perspective on different career paths¹. DCs are receiving a robust package of transferable skills, including communication, writing, data management, entrepreneurship and intellectual property rights (IPR) protection, suited to both academic and non-academic careers.

To date, all Doctoral Candidates (DCs) have participated in the first series of the Courses on Transferable Skills (CTS) held in Santiago de Compostela, alongside the Mid-term Check meeting in April 2024. These courses, conducted by Matical Innovation — a company specializing in the training, development, and management of international research projects — provided state-of-the-art instruction in communication, project management, and time management.

In addition, most of the fellows have engaged in local training, communication, and dissemination activities, as well as in online training sessions provided by the network.

This report includes the plans, outcomes, and review of the activities carried out during the project. It will be updated annually, as defined in the project's Description of Action, to ensure a comprehensive record of activities and maintain the quality of the project's implementation.

¹ [European Universities initiative](#)

2. OBJECTIVE

This annual report aims to report and analyse the quality of the implementation of the local training and networking activities carried out during the RBP-ReguNet Project.

3. Network's Courses on Transferable Skills

All participating scientists and DCs will contribute to the meetings and training events, and the hosting of events will be rotated between beneficiaries to maximise mobility of DCs. Five one-day (CTS) will provide transversal skills and competences to boost their scientific careers will be provided to DCs, part of the career development plan to incorporate trained talent to science and society. These courses are designed to broaden and deepen research skills such as leadership, scientific writing, or tech transfer. These courses will be divided in lectures given by experts in the field in the mornings followed by afternoon practical sessions where they will work on the skills to develop, e.g., designing, coordinating and executing a project from scratch in CTS2, or building up the three key components of a patent application in CTS4.

Additional online training, along with knowledge checks, will be made available to the DCs throughout the project. Furthermore, the newsletters will include suggestions for additional courses and online training opportunities for the fellows.

Overall, each DC will be expected to accumulate the equivalent to 30 ECTS credits in core research skills and transferable skills for their doctoral awards.

3.1. Courses on transferable skills (CTS)

3.1.1. CTS1&2 – Santiago de Compostela 4-5 April 2024

The first CTS series, which took place on April at CiMUS (Santiago de Compostela) integrated with the Mid-Term Check Meeting, focused on communication skills, and time and project management. We expect the courses will allow the fellows to acquire valuable knowledge and skills to optimize their individual projects and equip them to better face any encountered issues.

3.1.1.1. Programme

The outstanding programme designed by Matical Innovation S.L. and detailed below, offered a complete set of activities, practical examples and straight to the point lessons focused on communication, and time and project management.

DAY 0: PRE-TASKS

In order to make the most of the training days, the fellows should complete two simple tasks and send them to the trainers beforehand:

- *Exercise 1: Please prepare a short text (1 page maximum) on your pre-doctoral research. The text should address the following aspects:*
 - *A brief introduction to the topic*
 - *Need/problem addressed by your research*
 - *Solution (how your research intends to solve that problem/ satisfy that identified need)*
 - *What will be the significant outcome/ product of your project?*
 - *What are the main objectives that have been set to achieve that result*
 - *Who is behind this project (brief explanation about themselves)*

- *Exercise 2: Please prepare a short text (1/2 page max) about your main outcome/product. The text should address the following aspects (item followed by a short explanation (2 lines max):*
 - Main features
 - Advantages
 - Benefits

DAY 1: R+D+i PROJECT MANAGEMENT AND SCIENTIFIC WRITING

MODULE 1: HOW TO DEVELOP A WORK PLAN AND MANAGE AN R+D+i PROJECT EFFICIENTLY

Duration: 3h

SESSION 1: WORK PLAN

A correct planning of R+D+i projects ensures their proper execution in time, form and budget. However, it is not an easy task. During the session we will review with the doctoral students the key concepts that a good work plan must have, how to structure it, as well as the tools available. In this session we will work in a completely dynamic way, in groups, developing the work plan of a practical case proposed by us or by the doctoral students themselves aligned with their research projects. During the dynamic, we will make the doctoral students wear different hats: that of evaluator, that of coordinator of a consortium project, that of partner of a project. There is nothing more inspiring than seeing the problem from different perspectives.

SESSION 2: THE ROLE OF THE PROJECT MANAGER. HOW TO EXERCISE GOOD LEADERSHIP.

PhD students are called to occupy leadership positions in the near future that will take them from launching collaborations with other researchers or research groups, to promoting their own lines of research, through the coordination of collaborative R+D+i projects. However, leading work teams is an arduous task that in many cases ends up in disenchanted and non-proactive researchers. In this session we will give some keys on how to form a good work team or consortiums. We will also review the role of the coordinator at each stage of the project, from writing to execution. We will give the doctoral students some practical advice to face this task, from our experience as project managers and we will finish by reviewing what qualities make us exercise good leadership within the framework of R+D+i projects.

MODULE 2: SCIENTIFIC WRITING

Duration: 2h

SESSION 1: OPEN SCIENCE and FAIR PRINCIPLES IN DATA MANAGEMENT IN RESEARCH

As part of the development of Open Science, the European Commission requires all projects funded under the current Horizon Europe Programme, with justified exceptions, to develop a data management plan and ensure open access to research data. Data should be deposited in open following the FAIR principles that describe how research results should be organized so that they are findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable. Publishing data in accordance with the FAIR principles makes it possible to comply with the motto "as open as possible, as closed as necessary". During this session we will learn the fundamental principles as well as the tools available to comply with these policies.

DAY 2: COMMUNICATION

MODULE 3: WRITTEN COMMUNICATION

Duration: 2h

SESSION 1: CONVINCING THROUGH THE WRITTEN WORD

How we write is as important or more important than the content itself. The style, the quality of the language, the correct use of the language, will impact the message we want to convey. Writing for the reader and convincing you is key to achieving success. During this session we will review with the doctoral students some techniques of the so-called persuasive writing and we will share some practical tips.

SESSION 2: TELLING OUR RESEARCH

From participation in competitions for young researchers, to conferences, through networking environments, more and more frequently and in earlier stages of their research, doctoral students have to face different situations in which they have to tell in a brief and concise way what their research is about, what differentiates them from the rest, at the same time they need to generate a genuine interest in their interlocutor that makes them be remembered. Few golden minutes that can open doors to future collaborations, research stays, awards and even job opportunities, which do not leave room for improvisation. During this training, we will put into practice everything we learned during the previous session so that the doctoral students can prepare the pitch of their research project.

MODULE 4: VERBAL COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES

Duration: 3h

SESSION 1: THINK, STRUCTURE YOUR MIND AND COMMUNICATE

The speaker is the key actor in any communication process. During this session we will review the map of communication skills that you must have, as well as the leadership competencies linked to communication skills. We will also learn to structure our ideas in a simple and clear way with the ultimate goal of impacting and persuading our interlocutor. We will review techniques such as Storytelling and Visualthinking.

SESSION 2: HOW TO CUT TO THE CHASE AND BE REMEMBERED

Using three-stage plans helps to focus communication and lay out the analysis in a compelling and structured way. During this session we will learn how to provide our listeners with simple, memorable and unifying ideas, as well as how to rely on structured reasoning to interact with the audience and answer questions.

SESSION 3: NON-VERBAL COMMUNICATION

Nonverbal communication includes eye contact, gestures, etc. During this session we will highlight the importance of authentic gestures and learn how to develop a "start" position. We will also understand how we should adjust our speech based on the size of the audience.

The second part of the session will be dedicated to posture and movement, and how to use them to build confidence, avoid distractions, move with purpose, adjust the speed, variation, and modulation of our voice, reduce speaking errors, and project our voice effortlessly.

Finally, some volunteers will present their pitch in front of the rest of the colleagues who will act as a fictitious jury in which they will put into practice everything they have previously learned. Reviewing this, applying the knowledge learned, will help students improve through practice, as well as detect weak points that will need more future work.

3.1.1.2. Duration and structure of the training

The training was structured through modules dedicated to different thematic blocks, which were further divided into sessions. Each session consisted of an initial part where concepts were developed, tools were provided, and several practical examples were shown. This was followed by one or more individual or group dynamics that allowed participants to put into practice what they had learned in an enjoyable and fun way. These activities encouraged both critical and analytical thinking, as well as proactive participation from the doctoral students. These dynamics were likely the first collaborations among them, potentially planting the seed for future interactions within the project network.

The training was distributed over two days, each lasting five hours, with short breaks, and was preferably held in the morning. To ensure effective utilization of the sessions, it was recommended that the training be conducted face-to-face for groups of 10-15 researchers, in a large room equipped with worktables, a blackboard, and audiovisual media.

3.1.1.3. Evaluation

The training event was notably successful, evidenced by several key factors:

- **Full Attendance:** The training saw complete attendance over the two-day period, with no participants dropping out at any stage. This high level of engagement indicates a strong commitment to the training program and suggests that the content and delivery were sufficiently engaging to maintain participant interest throughout.
- **Completion of Planned Content and Activities:** All the planned content was successfully delivered, and every scheduled activity was completed. This demonstrates effective time management and thorough preparation by the facilitators, ensuring that the training objectives were fully met.
- **High Levels of Commitment and Performance:** Participants displayed a high level of commitment and performance, particularly during the practical activities and examples. Their active participation and evident interest in the content highlight the relevance and quality of the training materials and the effectiveness of the instructional methods used.
- **Post-Training Communication:** Post-training communication was maintained with all participants, facilitating the sharing of materials generated during the sessions, including videos, documents, and presentations. This ongoing engagement supports the reinforcement of learning outcomes and provides participants with valuable resources to refer to after the training, thereby enhancing the overall impact of the training program.

Overall, the training event was characterized by full engagement, comprehensive delivery of content, high participant commitment, and effective follow-up communication, all of which contributed to its success.

3.2. Upcoming CTS

3.2.1. CTS 3 – Beyond the Bench – Career development for scientists

A 1-day lecture-based session professionally organized focusing on project planning & research management, besides training on the CV writing, interview techniques and career planning.

3.2.2. CTS 4 – Crash Course on protection and valorisation of Intellectual Property

This 1-day course provides the main notions on the protection of research results and their valorisation.

3.2.3. CTS 5: Entrepreneurship & Company Management

In this 1-day session, members of the biotech sector inside and outside of the DN will cover aspects relating with business development (Projects in start-up and Biotech).

3.3. Online training

3.3.1. Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)

3.3.1.1. Content

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) is a key concept to consider when designing and carrying out biomedical research work, and an important training included in our project's proposal. To comply with this, we provided all RBP-ReguNet fellows with support material on RRI and Open Science based on several webinars and documents from the Association of European Research Libraries ([LIBER](#)), which is the voice of Europe's research library community. Then, we asked them to complete a knowledge check quiz on RRI we developed for them.

Webinar: Use Cases for Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)

[LIBER Webinar: Use Cases for Responsible Research and Innovation \(RRI\) \(youtube.com\)](#)

[LIBER Webinar: Use Cases for Responsible Research and Innovation \(zenodo.org\)](#)

Open Science Monitoring in Europe: A LIBER, UNESCO and LA Referencia Webinar

[Open Science Monitoring in Europe: A LIBER, UNESCO and LA Referencia Webinar \(youtube.com\)](#)

[LIBER, UNESCO and LA Referencia Webinar - Open Science Monitoring in Europe \(zenodo.org\)](#)

3.3.1.2. Evaluation

The evaluation consisted of a 4-options, single correct answer online test with 24 questions addressing some of the key concepts related to RRI. The quiz was designed in Microsoft Forms platform for a better convenience:

<https://forms.office.com/e/FAgDVHT4g9>

Results confirmed that the fellows followed and understood the content, achieving more than 90% of correct answers in average. Results can be displayed in the following link and in ANNEX I:

<https://forms.office.com/e/FAgDVHT4g9?origin=lprLink>

4. Local Training

Each DC fellow works on an individual research project, while enrolled in an official PhD doctoral program, either at their host beneficiary (where the beneficiary can award PhD title, USC, MRC-CVR, EMBL, UniTN, UMIL), or at local universities when the recipient cannot award a PhD degree (e.g. UPF in the case of CRG fellows, UniTN in the case of IMMAGINA, UvA for SANQUIN, and UPSaclay in the case of IC).

As part of the standard training and research programme, all fellows shall participate in internal activities such as lab meetings, journal clubs and institutional seminars that are available in each participating institution, where they will be exposed to latest results and ideas from fellow work colleagues and leading scientists, widening their background scientific knowledge and breadth of their own research projects (Table 1). DCs shall also receive specific technical training tailored to the needs of their individual projects, e.g. animal experimentation certifications, training in state-of-the-art technology and equipment, etc (Table 2).

In addition to planned outreach activities detailed in the Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (Deliverable 6.5), DCs shall also participate in outreach activities at the institutional level (open days, institutional events, etc.) or local community level, e.g., Cancer Awareness Month.

4.1. Scientific communication and dissemination activities

Table 1. Communication and dissemination activities.

DC	CLASS	EVENT TYPE	EVENT NAME	VENUE	DATE	PARTICIPATION	TITLE	AUTHORS
2	Communication	Meeting	FIBRONET Meeting	Madrid	20/05/2024	Attendee	FIBRONET Periodic Meeting	
4	Dissemination	Seminar	GENOME BIOLOGY DATA CLUB	Barcelona	15/07/2024	Chalk talk	PDIA6: an unconventional RNA-binding protein involved in melanoma progression	Zurkowska Dominika
4	Dissemination	Symposium	CRG PhD SYMPOSIUM	Barcelona	28-29/11/2024	Poster	Role of RNA-binding properties in PDIA6 biology and in melanoma progression	Zurkowska Dominika, Mestre-Farras Neus, Gebauer Fatima
6	Dissemination	Conference	Sanquin Science Day	Amsterdam	28/11/2023	Poster	T cell exhaustion Models	Hozjan Zan, Wolkers Monika
7	Communication	WORKSHOP	Glasgow Virology Workshop	Glasgow	04/06/2024	Organizing Committee Member	GLASGOW VIROLOGY WORKSHOP	
7	Dissemination		PGR Poster Day	Glasgow	31/05/2024	POSTER	Viruses Turn Autophagy on its Head using Riboregulation	Namah Raut, Rozeena Arif, Vincenzo Ruscica, Alfredo Castello

9	Dissemination	Seminar	19th Annual SIBBM Seminar - The time of molecular biology: development, homeostasis and aging	Trento	17-19/06/2024	Attendee		
9	Dissemination	Symposium	35th Pezcoller Symposium - Cancer as a systemic disease: interactions between tumor and host	Trento	24-25/06/2024	Attendee		
10	Dissemination	Conference	SCI Meeting	Milan	26/08/2023	Poster	Dealing with HuR Inhibitors	Hesse Salma, Seneci Pierfausto
10	Dissemination	Conference	SCI Meeting	Milan	26/08/2024	Poster	Structure-based design and synthesis of novel HUR inhibitors	Hesse Salma, Arosio, Daniela, Seneci Pierfausto
10	Dissemination	Conference	EFMC-ISMC	Rome	01/09/2024	Poster	Structure-based design and synthesis of novel HUR inhibitors	Hesse Salma, Arosio, Daniela, Seneci Pierfausto
10	Dissemination	Training school	Natural products in drug discovery: experimental and computational approaches	Naples	18/06/2024	Attendee	Rational design and synthesis of multi-targeted ligands	
11	Dissemination	Symposium	50th Anniversary Scientific Symposium:	Heidelberg	04-05/07/2024	Attendee	'From atoms to ecosystems – a new era in life sciences'	Rolf Apweiler, Elena Conti, Anne Ephrussi, Eileen Furlong, Cornelius Gross, Rainer Pepperkok, Pavel Tomancak, Nassos Typas

4.2. Local training activities

Table 2. Local training activities.

DC	TYPE OF TRAINING	CERTIFICATION	PLACE	TRAINER	START DATE	END DATE	UTILITY (0-100%)
1	ANIMAL EXPERIMENTATION	B&C	USC/CEBEGA	ANIMALARIA	15/02/2024	13/05/2024	80%
2	ANIMAL EXPERIMENTATION	B&C	USC/CEBEGA	ANIMALARIA	15/02/2024	13/05/2024	70%
3	Radioactivity: Handling and Radioprotection	Yes	IC	IC,FR	27/03/2024	27/03/2024	60%
3	Scientific Integrity	Yes	IC/PSL	IC/PSL,FR	06/10/2024	06/10/2024	100%

3	Preventing gender based sexual violence	Yes	Groupe EGAE	IC/EGAE,FR	02/08/2024	02/08/2024	100%
3	Crises environnementales: Understanding the issues and solutions	Yes	Universite Paris-Saclay,FR	Universite Paris-Saclay,FR	19/07/2024	19/07/2024	50%
3	Introduction to data management practices	Yes	Universite Paris-Saclay,FR	Universite Paris-Saclay,FR	15/07/2024	15/07/2024	80%
4	PRACTICAL WORKSHOP: iCLIP2	EMBO CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION	IIT/GENOA	EMBO	07/04/2024	12/04/2024	80%
4	Practical Course: R Programming Introduction	NO	CRG	CRG/TAO	12/03/2024	21/03/2024	60%
4	Practical Course: Biostatistics	NO	CRG	CRG/TAO	04/04/2024	13/06/2024	60%
7	R course for bioinformatics and data visualization	NO	UoG, UK	John Cole	12/06/2023	23/06/2023	100%
7	Let's Talk about Race in the Workplace.	NO	UoG, UK	University of Glasgow	27/06/2024	27/06/2024	50%
7	PGR Research Integrity.	NO	UoG, UK	University of Glasgow	28/06/2024	28/06/2024	80%
7	Introduction To The General Data Protection Regulation	NO	UoG, UK	University of Glasgow	12/04/2024	12/04/2024	60%
9	PRACTICAL COURSE: STATISTICAL METHODS FOR EXPERIMENT DESIGN AND DATA ANALYSIS	NO	UNITN	UNITN	30/01/2024	08/03/2024	60%
10	ADVANCED NMR TECHNIQUES	UniMI CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION	Milan	UniMI	20/02/2024	28/02/2024	80%

5. Monitoring and Reporting

Monitoring the training and its impact on the Doctoral Candidates' (DCs) work will depend on effective communication between the DCs, their supervisors, the Training & Doctoral Studies Committee, and the Project Management Team.

As part of the general progress monitoring program, DCs will hold weekly personal meetings with colleagues, supervisors, and/or co-supervisors at their institutions. Additional meetings with external co-supervisors, conducted via videoconferencing, will be arranged to assess and guide the progress of their projects and training, both within the network and locally. Moreover, some DCs will establish local or departmental Thesis Advisory Committees consisting of various internal and external advisers, providing them with an additional source of guidance and support for their PhD studies.

This report will be updated annually to allow both supervisors and the Training & Doctoral Studies Committee to evaluate the effectiveness of the training, its impact on the DCs' individual projects, and to adjust future actions according to the DC and/or group's needs. Templates for the reporting documents are available in the online repository.

6. DEVIATIONS

There are no identified deviations nor delays related to this deliverable.

ANNEX I. RRI Quiz Results

2. What is the primary goal of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)? (0 punto)

Un 100 % de los usuarios que completaron el cuestionario (8 de 8) respondió correctamente a esta pregunta.

[Más detalles](#)

- To increase the profitability of re... 0
- To engage society more broadly... 8 ✓
- To reduce the number of resear... 0
- To limit access to scientific results 0

3. Which of the following is NOT a key pillar of RRI? (0 punto)

Un 100 % de los usuarios que completaron el cuestionario (8 de 8) respondió correctamente a esta pregunta.

[Más detalles](#)

- Gender equality 0
- Ethical dimension 0
- Financial profitability 8 ✓
- None of the above 0

4. What stands in Article 27 of the Universal Declaration on Human Rights? (0 punto)

Un 100 % de los usuarios que completaron el cuestionario (8 de 8) respondió correctamente a esta pregunta.

[Más detalles](#)

- Everyone has the right freely to ... 8 ✓
- Nobody has de right to freely to... 0
- All scientific advancements mus... 0
- Scientists cannot share any scie... 0

5. What does RRI emphasize regarding access to scientific results? (0 punto)

Un 100 % de los usuarios que completaron el cuestionario (8 de 8) respondió correctamente a esta pregunta.

[Más detalles](#)

- Restricting access to only acade... 0
- Increasing access to scientific re... 8 ✓
- Charging high fees for access 0
- Limiting access to specific regions 0

6. RRI aims to ensure gender equality in which aspects? (0 punto)

Un 100 % de los usuarios que completaron el cuestionario (8 de 8) respondió correctamente a esta pregunta.

[Más detalles](#)

- In the research process 0
- In research content 0
- In the dissemination of results 0
- All of the above 8 ✓

7. What is the role of governance settings in RRI? (0 punto)

Un 100 % de los usuarios que completaron el cuestionario (8 de 8) respondió correctamente a esta pregunta.

[Más detalles](#)

- Anticipating and assessing pote... 8 ✓
- Focusing on societal expectations 0
- Focusing on technical aspects 0
- Prioritizing short-term results 0

8. What is the significance of promoting formal and informal science education in RRI? (0 punto)

Un 100 % de los usuarios que completaron el cuestionario (8 de 8) respondió correctamente a esta pregunta.

[Más detalles](#)

- To limit public understanding of... 0
- To enhance public engagement ... 8 ✓
- To increase the number of scien... 0
- To focus on formal education 0

9. Which of the following is a key aspect of engaging society in RRI? (0 punto)

Un 100 % de los usuarios que completaron el cuestionario (8 de 8) respondió correctamente a esta pregunta.

[Más detalles](#)

- Excluding experts from discussi... 0
- Broadly involving various societ... 8 ✓
- Limiting engagement to scientifi... 0
- Prioritizing corporate interests 0

10. How does RRI address the issue of gender equality? (0 punto)

Un 88 % de los usuarios que completaron el cuestionario (7 de 8) respondió correctamente a esta pregunta.

[Más detalles](#)

- By ignoring gender disparities 1
- By focusing only on male resear... 0
- By ensuring equal opportunities... 7 ✓
- By focusing only on female parti... 0

11. What is the importance of increasing access to scientific results in RRI? (0 punto)

Un 100 % de los usuarios que completaron el cuestionario (8 de 8) respondió correctamente a esta pregunta.

[Más detalles](#)

- To restrict information to a selec... 0
- To increase publication costs 0
- To limit the spread of information 0
- To democratize knowledge and ... 8 ✓

12. Which of the following best describes the approach of RRI towards societal expectations? (0 punto)

Un 88 % de los usuarios que completaron el cuestionario (7 de 8) respondió correctamente a esta pregunta.

[Más detalles](#)

- Limiting societal expectations 0
- Prioritizing scientific goals 0
- Anticipating and addressing soc... 7 ✓
- All of the above 1

13. What is the role of ethical considerations in RRI? (0 punto)

Un 100 % de los usuarios que completaron el cuestionario (8 de 8) respondió correctamente a esta pregunta.

[Más detalles](#)

- To be disregarded in favor of sci... 0
- To be considered only in clinical ... 0
- To be addressed only after resea... 0
- To be integrated into the resear... 8 ✓

14. How does RRI promote science education? (0 punto)

Un 88 % de los usuarios que completaron el cuestionario (7 de 8) respondió correctamente a esta pregunta.

[Más detalles](#)

- By limiting educational outreach 0
- By focusing on non-academic a... 0
- By focusing only on higher educ... 1
- By promoting both formal and i... 7 ✓

15. What is the significance of designing governance settings in RRI? (0 punto)

Un 100 % de los usuarios que completaron el cuestionario (8 de 8) respondió correctamente a esta pregunta.

[Más detalles](#)

- To facilitate the implementation ... 8 ✓
- To centralize control 0
- To increase stakeholder involve... 0
- To prioritize corporate governan... 0

16. Which of the following is a key outcome of engaging society in RRI? (0 punto)

Un 100 % de los usuarios que completaron el cuestionario (8 de 8) respondió correctamente a esta pregunta.

[Más detalles](#)

- Reduced public interest in science 0
- Enhanced public trust and colla... 8 ✓
- Increased research costs 0
- Limited innovation 0

17. What does RRI aim to achieve through gender equality in research? (0 punto)

Un 100 % de los usuarios que completaron el cuestionario (8 de 8) respondió correctamente a esta pregunta.

[Más detalles](#)

- To alter the status quo 0
- To ensure diverse perspectives a... 8 ✓
- To focus only on male-dominate... 0
- To limit female participation 0

18. How does RRI address the ethical dimension in research? (0 punto)

Un 100 % de los usuarios que completaron el cuestionario (8 de 8) respondió correctamente a esta pregunta.

[Más detalles](#)

- By reducing ethical concerns 0
- By focusing on productivity 0
- By integrating ethical considerat... 8 ✓
- By limiting ethical reviews 0

19. What is the role of public engagement in RRI? (0 punto)

Un 100 % de los usuarios que completaron el cuestionario (8 de 8) respondió correctamente a esta pregunta.

[Más detalles](#)

- To involve a broad range of soci... 8 ✓
- To exclude non-experts 0
- To prioritize academic interests 0
- To limit public input 0

20. Which of the following is NOT an objective of the FIT4RRI project training tools and actions? (0 punto)

Un 88 % de los usuarios que completaron el cuestionario (7 de 8) respondió correctamente a esta pregunta.

[Más detalles](#)

- To provide an eLearning environ... 0
- To review collected training mat... 0
- To offer financial incentives for c... 7 ✓
- To conduct training on RRI and ... 1

21. What is the main benefit of systematically organised online training materials? (0 punto)

Un 100 % de los usuarios que completaron el cuestionario (8 de 8) respondió correctamente a esta pregunta.

[Más detalles](#)

- They are free of charge 0
- They ensure quality and organis... 8 ✓
- They provide financial incentives 0
- They offer entertainment 0

22. What is the purpose of linking learning experiences to institutional practices? (0 punto)

Un 100 % de los usuarios que completaron el cuestionario (8 de 8) respondió correctamente a esta pregunta.

[Más detalles](#)

- To increase the number of enroll... 0
- To ensure the practical applicati... 8 ✓
- To reduce the workload of instr... 0
- To provide a fun way to learn 0

23. What is the connection between Research Integrity and Responsible Research? (0 punto)

Un 88 % de los usuarios que completaron el cuestionario (7 de 8) respondió correctamente a esta pregunta.

[Más detalles](#)

- They are unrelated concepts 0
- Research Integrity is a subset of ... 7 ✓
- RRI is a subset of Research Integ... 1
- Both focus on maximizing profits 0

24. What opportunities exist for institutions to start implementing responsible research practices? (0 punto)

Un 100 % de los usuarios que completaron el cuestionario (8 de 8) respondió correctamente a esta pregunta.

[Más detalles](#)

- None, as RRI is not practical 0
- Collaborating with industry to in... 0
- Integrating RRI into research pr... 8 ✓
- Generating societal needs 0

25. What is the primary goal of Open Science programs? (0 punto)

Un 100 % de los usuarios que completaron el cuestionario (8 de 8) respondió correctamente a esta pregunta.

[Más detalles](#)

- To increase implication of under... 0
- To enhance research transparen... 8 ✓
- To promote competition among... 0
- To prioritize interdisciplinary work 0

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